

Global PAC Bounds for Learning Discrete Time Markov Chains

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Abstract Learning models from observations of a system is a powerful tool with many applications. In this paper, we consider learning Discrete Time Markov Chains (DTMC), with different methods such as *frequency estimation* or *Laplace smoothing*. While models learnt with such methods converge asymptotically towards the exact system, a more practical question in the realm of trusted machine learning is how accurate a model learnt with a limited time budget is. Existing approaches provide bounds on how close the model is to the original system, in terms of bounds on *local* (transition) probabilities, which has unclear implication on the *global* behavior.

In this work, we provide *global bounds on the error* made by such a learning process, in terms of global behaviors formalized using *temporal logic*. More precisely, we propose a learning process ensuring a bound on the error in the probabilities of these properties. While such learning process cannot exist for the full LTL logic, we provide one ensuring a bound that is uniform over all the formulas of CTL. Further, given one time-to-failure property, we provide an improved learning algorithm. Interestingly, frequency estimation is sufficient for the latter, while Laplace smoothing is needed to ensure non-trivial uniform bounds for the full CTL logic.

1 Introduction

Discrete-Time Markov Chains (DTMC) are commonly used in model checking to model the behavior of stochastic systems [2,3,6,25]. A DTMC is described by a set of states and transition probabilities between these states. The main issue with modeling stochastic systems using DTMCs is to obtain the transition probabilities. One appealing approach to overcome this issue is to observe the system and to *learn automatically* these transition probabilities [7,29], e.g., using frequency estimation or Laplace (or additive) smoothing [11]. Frequency estimation works by observing a long run of the system and estimating each individual transition by its empirical frequency. However, in this case, the unseen transitions are estimated as zeros. Once the probability of a transition is set to zero, the probability to reach a state could be tremendously changed, e.g., from 1 to 0 if the probability of this transition in the system is small but non-zero.

To overcome this problem, when the set of transitions with non-zero probability is known (but not their probabilities), Laplace smoothing assigns a positive probability to the unseen transitions, i.e., by adding a small quantity both to the numerator and the denominator of the estimate used in frequency estimation. Other smoothing methods exist, such as Good-Turing [14] and Kneser-Sey estimations [6], notably used in natural language processing. Notwithstanding smoothing generates estimation biases, all these methods converge asymptotically to the exact transition probabilities.

In practice, however, there is often limited budget in observing and learning from the system, and the validity of the learned model is in question. In the realm of trusted machine learning, it is thus crucial to measure how the learned model differs from the original system and to provide practical guidelines (e.g., on the number of observations) to guarantee some control of their divergence.

Comparing two Markov processes is a common problem that relies on a notion of divergence. Most existing approaches focus on deviations between the probabilities of local transitions (e.g. [9,26,4]). However, a single deviation in a transition probability between the original system and the learned model may lead to large differences in their global behaviors. For instance, the probability of reaching certain state may be magnified by paths which go through the same deviated transition many times. It is thus important to use a measure that quantifies the differences over global behaviors, rather than simply checking whether the differences between the individual transition probabilities are low enough.

In this work, we model global behaviors using temporal logics. We consider Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) [23] and Computational Tree Logic (CTL) [10]. Agreeing on all formulas of LTL means that the first order behaviors of the system and the model are the same, while agreeing on CTL means that the system and the model are bisimilar [1]. Our goal is to provide stopping rules in the learning process of DTMCs that provides Probably Approximately Correct (PAC) bounds on the error in probabilities of every property in the logic between the model and the system. In Section 2, we recall useful notions on DTMCs and PAC-learning. We point out related works in Section 3. Our main contributions are as follows:

- In Section 4, we show that it is impossible to learn a DTMC accurate for all LTL formulas, by adapting a result from [12].
- We provide in Section 6 a learning process bounding the difference in probability *uniformly over all CTL properties*. To do so, we use Laplace smoothing, and we provide rationale on choosing the smoothing parameter.
- For the particular case of a time-to-failure property, notably used to compute the mean time between failures of critical systems (see e.g. [24]), we provide tighter bounds in Section 5, based on frequency estimation.

2 Background

In this section, we introduce the notions and notations used throughout the paper. A stochastic system \mathcal{S} is interpreted as a set of interacting components

in which the state is determined randomly with respect to a global probability measure described below.

Definition 1 (Discrete-Time Markov Chains). A Discrete-Time Markov Chain is a triple $\mathcal{M} = (S, \mu, A)$ where:

- S is a finite set of states;
- $\mu : S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is an initial probability distribution over S ;
- $A : S \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a transition probability matrix, such that for every $s \in S$, $\sum_{s' \in S} A(s, s') = 1$.

We denote m the cardinal of S and $A = (a_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq m} = (A(i, j))_{1 \leq i, j \leq m}$ the probability matrix. Figs. 1 and 2 show the graph of two DTMCs over 3 states $\{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$ (with $\mu(s_1) = 1$). A run is an infinite sequence $\omega = s_0 s_1 \dots$ and a path is a finite sequence $\omega = s_0 \dots s_l$ such that $\mu(s_0) > 0$ and $A(s_i, s_{i+1}) > 0$ for all i , $0 \leq i \leq l$. The length $|\omega|$ of a path ω is its number of transitions.

The cylinder set of ω , denoted $C(\omega)$, consists of all the runs starting by a path ω . Markov chain \mathcal{M} underlies a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, where Ω is the set of all runs from \mathcal{M} ; \mathcal{F} is the sigma-algebra generated by all the cylinders $C(\omega)$ and \mathbb{P} is the unique probability measure [30] such that $\mathbb{P}(C(s_0 \dots s_l)) = \mu(s_0) \prod_{i=1}^l A(s_{i-1}, s_i)$. For simplicity, we assume a unique initial state s_0 and denote $\mathbb{P}(\omega) = \mathbb{P}(C(\omega))$. Finally, we sometimes use the notation \mathbb{P}_i^A to emphasize that the probability distribution is parameterized by the probability matrix A , and the starting state is i .

2.1 PAC-learning for properties

To analyze the behavior of a system, properties are specified in temporal logic (e.g., LTL or CTL, respectively introduced in [23] and [10]). Given a logic \mathcal{L} and φ a property of \mathcal{L} , decidable in finite time, we denote $\omega \models \varphi$ if a path ω satisfies φ . Let $z : \Omega \times \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be the function that assigns 1 to a path ω if $\omega \models \varphi$ and 0 otherwise. In what follows, we assume that we have a procedure that draws path ω with respect to \mathbb{P}^A and outputs $z(\omega, \varphi)$. Further, we denote $\gamma(A, \varphi)$ the probability that a path drawn with respect to \mathbb{P}^A satisfies φ . We omit the property or the matrix in the notation when it is clear from the context. Finally, note that the behavior of $z(\cdot, \varphi)$ can be modeled as a Bernoulli random variable Z_φ parameterized by the mean value $\gamma(A, \varphi)$.

Figure 1: An example of DTMC \mathcal{M}_1

Figure 2: DTMC \mathcal{M}_2

Probably Approximately Correct (PAC) learning [27] is a framework for mathematical analysis of machine learning. Given $\varepsilon > 0$ and $0 < \delta < 1$, we say that a property φ of \mathcal{L} is PAC-learnable if there is an algorithm \mathcal{A} such that, given a sample of n paths drawn according to the procedure, with probability of at least $1 - \delta$, \mathcal{A} outputs in polynomial time (in $1/\varepsilon$ and $1/\delta$) an approximation of the average value for Z_φ close to its exact value, up to an error less than or equal to ε . Formally, φ is PAC-learnable if and only if \mathcal{A} outputs an approximation $\hat{\gamma}$ such that:

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma - \hat{\gamma}| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta \quad (1)$$

Moreover, if the above statement for algorithm \mathcal{A} is true for every property in \mathcal{L} , we say that \mathcal{A} is a PAC-learning algorithm for \mathcal{L} .

2.2 Monte-Carlo estimation and algorithm of Chen

Given a sample W of n paths drawn according to \mathbb{P}^A until φ is satisfied or violated (for φ such that with probability 1, φ is eventually satisfied or violated), the crude Monte-Carlo estimator, denoted $\hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi)$, of the mean value for the random variable Z_φ is given by the empirical frequency: $\hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n z(\omega_i) \approx \gamma(A, \varphi)$.

The Okamoto inequality [22] (also called the Chernoff bound in the literature) is often used to guarantee that the deviation between a Monte-Carlo estimator $\hat{\gamma}_W$ and the exact value γ by more than $\varepsilon > 0$ is bounded by a predefined confidence parameter δ . However, several sequential algorithms have been recently proposed to guarantee the same confidence and accuracy with fewer samples¹. In what follows, we use the algorithm of Chen [5].

Theorem 1 (Chen bound). *Let $\varepsilon > 0$, δ such that $0 < \delta < 1$ and $\hat{\gamma}_W$ be the crude Monte-Carlo estimator, based on n samples, of probability γ .*

$$\text{If } n \geq \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2} \log\left(\frac{2}{\delta}\right) \left[\frac{1}{4} - \left(\frac{1}{2} - \hat{\gamma}_W - \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon\right)^2\right],$$

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma - \hat{\gamma}_W| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta.$$

To ease the readability, we write $n_{\text{succ}} = \sum_{i=1}^n z(\omega_i)$ and $H(n, n_{\text{succ}}, \varepsilon, \delta) = \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2} \log\left(\frac{2}{\delta}\right) \left[\frac{1}{4} - \left(\frac{1}{2} - \hat{\gamma}_W - \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon\right)^2\right]$. When it is clear from the context, we only write $H(n)$. Then, the algorithm \mathcal{A} that stops sampling as soon as $n \geq H(n)$ and outputs a crude Monte-Carlo estimator for $\gamma(A, \varphi)$ is a PAC-learning algorithm for φ . The condition over n is called the stopping criteria of the algorithm. As far as we know, this algorithm requires fewer samples than the other sequential algorithms (see e.g., [18]). Note that the estimation of a probability close to $1/2$ likely requires more samples since $H(n)$ is maximized in $\hat{\gamma}_W = 1/2$.

¹ We recall the Okamoto-Chernoff bound in the extended version, Appendix B [17] but we do not use it in this work.

3 Related work

Our work shares similar statistical results (see Section 2.3) with Statistical Model Checking (SMC) [30]. However, the context and the outputs are different. SMC is a simulation-based approach that aims to estimate one probability for a given property [8,28], within acceptable margins of error and confidence [16,18,31]. A challenge in SMC is posed by unbounded properties (e.g., fairness) since the sampled executions are finite. Some algorithms have been proposed to handle unbounded properties but they require the knowledge of the minimal probability transition of the system [13], which is not possible in our context where we do not know the probabilities of transitions (and that is why we want to learn them!).

For comparison, our final output is the (approximated) transition matrix of a DTMC rather than one (approximated) probability of a given property. This learned DTMC can be used for different purposes, e.g. as a component in a bigger model or as a simulation tool. In terms of performances, we will show that we can learn a DTMC wrt a given property with the same number of samples as we need to estimate this property using SMC (see Section 5). That is, there is no penalty to estimate a DTMC rather than estimate one probability, and we can scale as well as SMC. In terms of expressivity, we can handle unbounded properties (e.g. fairness properties). Even better, we can learn a DTMC accurate uniformly over a possibly infinite set of properties, e.g. all formulas of CTL. This is something SMC is not designed to achieve.

Other related work can be cited: In [12], the authors investigate several distances for the estimation of the difference between DTMCs. But they do not propose algorithms for learning. In [15], the authors propose to analyze the learned model a posteriori to test whether it has some good properties. If not, then they tweak the model in order to enforce these properties. Also, several PAC-learning algorithms have been proposed for the estimation of stochastic systems [4,9] but these works focus on local transitions instead of global properties.

4 Problem statement

In this work, we are interested to learn a DTMC model from a stochastic system \mathcal{S} such that the behaviors of the system and the model are similar. We assume that the original system is a DTMC parameterized by a matrix A of transition probabilities. The transition probabilities are unknown, but the set of states of the DTMC is assumed to be known.

Our goal is to provide a learning algorithm \mathcal{A} that guarantees an accurate estimation of \mathcal{S} with respect to certain global properties. For that, a sampling process is defined as follows. A path (i.e., a sequence of states from s_0) of \mathcal{S} is observed, and at steps specified by the sampling process, a reset action is performed, setting \mathcal{S} back to its initial state s_0 . Then another path is generated. This process generates a set W of paths, called traces, used to learn a matrix \hat{A}_W . Formally, we want to provide a learning algorithm that guarantees the

following specification:

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{D}(A, \hat{A}_W) > \varepsilon) \leq \delta \quad (2)$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\delta > 0$ are respectively *accuracy* and *confidence* parameters and $\mathcal{D}(A, \hat{A}_W)$ is a measure of the divergence between A and \hat{A}_W .

There exist several ways to specify the divergence between two transition matrices, e.g., the Kullback-Leibler divergence [19] or a distance based on a matrix norm. However, the existing notions remain heuristic because they are based on the difference between the individual probabilistic transitions of the matrix. We argue that what matters in practice is often to quantify the similarity between the global behaviors of the systems and the learned model.

In order to specify the behaviors of interest, we use a property φ or a set of properties Ψ on the set of states visited. We are interested in the difference between the probabilities of φ (i.e., the measure of the set of runs satisfying φ) with respect to A and \hat{A}_W . We want to ensure that this difference is less than some predefined ε with (high) probability $1 - \delta$. Hence, we define:

$$\mathcal{D}_\varphi(A, \hat{A}_W) = |\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)| \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{D}_\Psi(A, \hat{A}_W) = \max_{\varphi \in \Psi} (\mathcal{D}_\varphi(A, \hat{A}_W)) \quad (4)$$

Our problem is to construct an algorithm which takes the following as inputs:

- confidence δ , $0 < \delta < 1$,
- absolute error $\varepsilon > 0$, and
- a property φ (or a set of properties Ψ),

and provides a learning procedure sampling a set W of paths, outputs \hat{A}_W , and terminates the sampling procedure while fulfilling Specification (2), with $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}_\varphi$ ($= \mathcal{D}_\Psi$).

In what follows, we assume that the confidence level δ and absolute error ε are fixed. We first start with a negative result: if Ψ is the set of LTL formulas [1], such a learning process is impossible.

Theorem 2. *Given $\varepsilon > 0$, $0 < \delta < 1$, and a finite set W of paths randomly drawn with respect to a DTMC A , there is no learning strategy such that, for every LTL formula φ ,*

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta \quad (5)$$

Note that contrary to Theorem 1, the deviation in Theorem 2 is a difference between two exact probabilities (of the original system and of a learned model). The theorem holds as long as \hat{A}_W and A are not strictly equal, no matter how \hat{A}_W is learned. To prove this theorem, we show that, for any number of observations, we can always define a sequence of LTL properties that violates the specification above. It only exploits a single deviation in one transition. The proof, inspired by a result from [12], is given in the extended version, Appendices B and C [17].

5 Learning for a time-to-failure property

In this section, we focus on property φ of reaching a failure state s_F from an initial state s_0 without re-passing by the initial state, which is often used for assessing the failure rate of a system and the mean time between failures (see e.g., [24]). We assume that with probability 1, the runs eventually re-pass by s_0 or reach s_F . Also, without loss of generality, we assume that there is a unique failure state s_F in A . We denote $\gamma(A, \varphi)$ the probability, given DTMC A , of satisfying property φ , i.e., the probability of a failure between two visits of s_0 .

Assume that the stochastic system \mathcal{S} is observed from state s_0 . Between two visits of s_0 , property φ can be monitored. If s_F is observed between two instances of s_0 , we say that the path $\omega = s_0 \cdot \rho \cdot s_F$ satisfies φ , with $s_0, s_F \notin \rho$. Otherwise, if s_0 is visited again from s_0 , then we say that the path $\omega = s_0 \cdot \rho \cdot s_0$ violates φ , with $s_0, s_F \notin \rho$. We call *traces* paths of the form $\omega = s_0 \cdot \rho \cdot (s_0 \vee s_F)$ with $s_0, s_F \notin \rho$. In the following, we show that it is sufficient to use a *frequency estimator* to learn a DTMC which provides a good approximate for such a property.

5.1 Frequency estimation of a DTMC

Given a set W of n traces, we denote n_{ij}^W the number of times transition from state i to state j occurred and n_i^W the number of times a transition has been taken from state i .

The *frequency estimator* of A is the DTMC $\hat{A}_W = (\hat{a}_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq m}$ given by $\hat{a}_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}$ for all i, j , with $\sum_{i=1}^m n_i^W = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m n_{ij}^W = |W|$. In other words, to learn \hat{A}_W , it suffices to count the number of times a transition from i to j occurred, and divide by the number of times state i has been observed. The matrix \hat{A}_W is trivially a DTMC, except for states i which have not been visited. In this case, one can set $\hat{a}_{ij} = \frac{1}{m}$ for all state j and obtain a DTMC. This has no impact on the behavior of \hat{A}_W as i is not reachable from s_0 in \hat{A}_W .

Let \hat{A}_W be the matrix learned using the frequency estimator from the set W of traces, and let A be the real probabilistic matrix of the original system \mathcal{S} . We show that, in the case of time-to-failure properties, $\gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)$ is equal to the crude Monte Carlo estimator $\hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi)$ induced by W .

5.2 PAC bounds for a time-to-failure property

We start by stating the main result of this section, bounding the error between $\gamma(A, \varphi)$ and $\gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)$:

Theorem 3. *Given a set W of n traces such that $n = \lceil H(n) \rceil$, we have:*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)| > \varepsilon \right) \leq \delta \quad (6)$$

where \hat{A}_W is the frequency estimator of A .

To prove Theorem (3), we first invoke Theorem 1 to establish:

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi)| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta \quad (7)$$

It remains to show that $\hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi) = \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)$:

Proposition 1. *Given a set W of traces, $\gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi) = \hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi)$.*

It might be appealing to think that this result can be proved by induction on the size of the traces, mimicking the proof of computation of reachability probabilities by linear programming [1]. This is actually not the case. The remaining of this section is devoted to proving Proposition (1).

We first define $q_W(u)$ the number of occurrences of sequence u in the traces of W . Note that u can be a state, an individual transition or even a path. We also use the following definitions in the proof.

Definition 2 (Equivalence). *Two sets of traces W and W' are equivalent if for all $s, t \in S$, $\frac{q_W(s \cdot t)}{q_W(s)} = \frac{q_{W'}(s \cdot t)}{q_{W'}(s)}$.*

We define a set of traces W' equivalent with W , implying that $\hat{A}_W = \hat{A}_{W'}$. This set W' of traces satisfies the following:

Lemma 1. *For any set of traces W , there exists a set of traces W' such that:*

- (i) W and W' are equivalent,
- (ii) for all $r, s, t \in S$, $q_{W'}(r \cdot s \cdot t) = \frac{q_{W'}(r \cdot s) \times q_{W'}(s \cdot t)}{q_{W'}(s)}$.

The proof of Lemma 1 is provided in [17] (see Appendix D). In Lemma 1, (i) ensures that $\hat{A}_{W'} = \hat{A}_W$ and (ii) ensures the equality between the proportion of runs of W' passing by s and satisfying γ , denoted $\hat{\gamma}_{W'}^s$, and the probability of reaching s_F before s_0 starting from s with respect to $\hat{A}_{W'}$. Formally,

Lemma 2. *For all $s \in S$, $\mathbb{P}_s^{\hat{A}_{W'}}(\text{reach } s_f \text{ before } s_0) = \hat{\gamma}_{W'}^s$.*

Proof. Let S_0 be the set of states s with no path in $\hat{A}_{W'}$ from s to s_f without passing through s_0 . For all $s \in S_0$, let $p_s = 0$. Also, let $p_{s_f} = 1$. Let $S_1 = S \setminus (S_0 \cup \{s_f\})$. Consider the system of equations (8) with variables $(p_s)_{s \in S_1} \in [0, 1]^{|S_1|}$:

$$\forall s \in S_1, \quad p_s = \sum_{t=1}^m \hat{A}_{W'}(s, t) p_t \quad (8)$$

The system of equations (8) admits a unique solution according to [1] (Theorem 10.19. page 766). Then, $(\mathbb{P}_s^{\hat{A}_{W'}}(\text{reach } s_f \text{ before } s_0))_{s \in S_1}$ is trivially a solution of (8). But, since W' satisfies the conditions of Lemma 1, we also have that $(\hat{\gamma}_{W'}^s)_{s \in S_1}$ is a solution of (8), and thus we have the desired equality. \square

Notice that Lemma 2 does not hold in general with the set W . We have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\gamma}_W(A, \varphi) &= \hat{\gamma}_W^{s_0} \quad (\text{by definition}) \\
&= \hat{\gamma}_{W'}^{s_0} \quad (\text{by Lemma 1}) \\
&= \mathbb{P}_{s_0}^{\hat{A}_{W'}}(\text{reach } s_f \text{ before } s_0) \quad (\text{by Lemma 2}) \\
&= \mathbb{P}_{s_0}^{\hat{A}_W}(\text{reach } s_f \text{ before } s_0) \quad (\text{by Lemma 1}) \\
&= \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi) \quad (\text{by definition}).
\end{aligned}$$

That concludes the proof of Proposition 1. It shows that learning can be as efficient as statistical model-checking on comparable properties.

6 Learning for the full CTL logic

In this section, we learn a DTMC \hat{A}_W such that \hat{A}_W and A have similar behaviors over all CTL formulas. This provides a much stronger result than on time-to-failure property, e.g., properties can involve liveness and fairness, and more importantly they are not known before the learning. Notice that PCTL [1] cannot be used, since an infinitesimal error on one > 0 probability can change the probability of a PCTL formula from 0 to 1. CTL is defined as follows:

Definition 3. *Let Prop be the set of state names. CTL is defined by the following grammar $\varphi ::= \perp \mid \top \mid p \mid \neg\varphi \mid \varphi \wedge \varphi \mid \varphi \vee \varphi \mid \varphi \wedge \varphi \mid \mathbf{AX}\varphi \mid \mathbf{EX}\varphi \mid \mathbf{AF}\varphi \mid \mathbf{EF}\varphi \mid \mathbf{AF}\varphi \mid \mathbf{EG}\varphi \mid \mathbf{AG}\varphi \mid \mathbf{E}(\varphi\mathbf{U}\varphi) \mid \mathbf{A}(\varphi\mathbf{U}\varphi)$, with $p \in \text{Prop}$. \mathbf{E} (exists) and \mathbf{A} (ll) are quantifiers on paths, \mathbf{neXt} , \mathbf{G} lobally, \mathbf{F} inally and \mathbf{U} ntil are path-specific quantifiers. Notice that some operators are redundant. A minimal set of operators is $\{\top, \vee, \neg, \mathbf{EG}, \mathbf{EU}, \mathbf{EX}\}$.*

As we want to compute the probability of paths satisfying a CTL formula, we consider formulas where the highest operator is not quantified over paths (without \mathbf{E} or \mathbf{A}). That is, Ψ is the set of formulas φ of the form $\varphi = \mathbf{X}\varphi_1$, $\varphi = \varphi_1\mathbf{U}\varphi_2$, $\varphi = \mathbf{F}\varphi_1$ or $\varphi = \mathbf{G}\varphi_1$, with φ_1, φ_2 CTL formulas. In particular, φ_1, φ_2 can be quantified over paths (only the topmost operator is not). For instance, the property considered in the previous section is $(\neg s_0)\mathbf{U}s_F$.

In this section, for the sake of simplicity, the finite set W of traces is obtained by observing paths till a state is seen twice on the path. Then, the reset action is used and another trace is obtained from another path. That is, a trace ω from W is of the form $\omega = \rho \cdot s \cdot \rho' \cdot s$, with $\rho \cdot s \cdot \rho'$ a loop-free path.

We need an additional hypothesis. We assume that the support of transition probabilities is known, i.e., for any state i , we know the set of states j such that $a_{ij} \neq 0$. This assumption is needed both for Theorem 5 and to apply Laplace smoothing. We will show that this property is necessary in Section 6.3.

6.1 Learning DTMCs with Laplace smoothing

Let $\alpha > 0$. For any state s , let k_s be the number of successors of s , that we know by hypothesis, and $T = \sum_{s \in S} k_s$ be the number of non-zero transitions. Let W

be a set of traces, n_{ij}^W the number of transitions from state i to state j , and $n_i^W = \sum_j n_{ij}^W$. The *estimator for W with Laplace smoothing α* is the DTMC $\hat{A}_W^\alpha = (\hat{a}_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq m}$ given for all i, j by:

$$\hat{a}_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}^W + \alpha}{n_i^W + k_i \alpha} \text{ if } a_{ij} \neq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{a}_{ij} = 0 \text{ otherwise}$$

In comparison with the frequency estimator, the Laplace smoothing adds for each state s a term α to the numerator and k_s times α to the denominator. This preserves the fact that \hat{A}_W^α is a Markov chain, and it ensures that $\hat{a}_{ij} \neq 0$ iff $a_{ij} \neq 0$. In particular, compared with the frequency estimator, it avoids creating zeros in the probability tables.

6.2 Conditioning and Probability Bounds

Using Laplace smoothing slightly changes the probability of each transition by say an additive offset η . We now explain how this small error η impacts the error on the probability of a CTL property.

Let A be a DTMC, and A_η be a DTMC such that $A_\eta(i, j) \neq 0$ iff $A(i, j) \neq 0$ for all states i, j , and such that $\sum_j |A_\eta(i, j) - A(i, j)| \leq \eta$ for all state i . For all state $s \in S$, let $R(s)$ be the set of states i such that there exists a path from i to s . Let $R_*(s) = R(s) \setminus \{s\}$. Since both DTMCs have the same support, R (and also R_*) is equal for A and A_η . Given m the number of states, the conditioning of A for $s \in S$ and $\ell \leq m$ is:

$$\text{Cond}_s^\ell(A) = \min_{i \in R_*(s)} \mathbb{P}_i^A(\mathbf{F}_{\leq \ell} \neg R_*(s))$$

i.e., the minimal probability from state $i \in R_*(s)$ to move away from $R_*(s)$ in at most ℓ steps. Let ℓ_s minimal such that $\text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A) > 0$. This minimal ℓ_s exists as $\text{Cond}_s^m(A) > 0$ since, for all $s \in S$ and $i \in R_*(s)$, there is at least one path reaching s from i (this path leaves $R_*(s)$), and taking a cycle-free path, we obtain a path of length at most m . Thus, the probability $\mathbb{P}_i^A(\mathbf{F}_{\leq m} \neg R_*(s))$ is at least the positive probability of the cylinder defined by this finite path. Formally,

Theorem 4. *Denoting φ the property of reaching state s in DTMC A , we have:*

$$|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(A_\eta, \varphi)| < \frac{\ell_s \cdot \eta}{\text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A)}$$

The proof of Theorem 4 is given in the extended version, Appendix E [17]. We can extend this result from reachability to formulas of the form $S_0 \mathbf{U} S_F$, where S_0, S_F are subsets of states. This formula means that we reach the set of states S_F through only states in S_0 on the way.

We define $R(S_0, S_F)$ to be the set of states which can reach S_F using only states of S_0 , and $R_*(S_0, S_F) = R(S_0, S_F) \setminus S_F$. For $\ell \in \mathbb{N}$, we let:

$$\text{Cond}_{S_0, S_F}^\ell(A) = \min_{i \in R_*(S_0, S_F)} \mathbb{P}_i^A(\mathbf{F}_{\leq \ell} \neg R_*(S_0, S_F) \vee \neg S_0).$$

Now, one can remark that $\text{Cond}_{S_0, S_F}(A) \geq \text{Cond}_{S, S_F}(A) > 0$. Let $\text{Cond}_{S_F}^\ell(A) = \text{Cond}_{S, S_F}^\ell(A)$. We have $\text{Cond}_{S_0, S_F}^\ell(A) \geq \text{Cond}_{S_F}^\ell(A)$. As before, we let $\ell_{S_F} \leq m$ be the minimal ℓ such that $\text{Cond}_{S_F}^\ell(A) > 0$, and obtain:

Theorem 5. *Denoting φ the property $S_0 \mathbf{U}_{S_F}$, we have, given DTMC A :*

$$|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(A_\eta, \varphi)| < \frac{\ell_{S_F} \cdot \eta}{\text{Cond}_{S_F}^{\ell_{S_F}}(A)}$$

We can actually improve this conditioning: we defined it as the probability to reach S_F or $S \setminus R(S, S_F)$. At the price of a more technical proof, we can obtain a better bound by replacing S_F by the set of states $R_1(S_F)$ that have probability 1 to reach S_F . We let $\overline{R}_*(S_F) = R(S, S_F) \setminus R_1(S_F)$ the set of states that can reach S_F with < 1 probability, and

$$\overline{\text{Cond}}_{S_F}^\ell(A) = \min_{i \in \overline{R}_*(S_F)} \mathbb{P}_i^A(\mathbf{F}_{\leq \ell} \neg \overline{R}_*(S_F))$$

6.3 Optimality and necessity of knowing the transitions support

We show now that the bound we provide in Theorems 4 and 5 are close to optimal, and that the hypothesis on $A(i, j) \neq 0$ iff $A_\eta(i, j) \neq 0$ is necessary.

Let us consider DTMCs A, \hat{A}, \hat{B} in Fig. 3 and formula $\mathbf{F} s_2$ stating that s_2 is eventually reached. The probabilities to satisfy this formula in A, \hat{A}, \hat{B} are respectively $\mathbb{P}^A(\mathbf{F} s_2) = \frac{1}{2}$, $\mathbb{P}^{\hat{A}}(\mathbf{F} s_2) = \frac{2\tau + \eta}{4\tau}$ and $\mathbb{P}^{\hat{B}}(\mathbf{F} s_2) = 0$.

Assume that A is the real system and that \hat{A} and \hat{B} are DTMCs we learned from A .

As we do not know precisely the transition probabilities in A , we can only compute the conditioning on \hat{A} and not on A . We have $R(s_2) = \{s_1, s_2\}$ and $R_*(s_2) = \overline{R}_*(s_2) = \{s_1\}$. The probability to stay in $R_*(s_2)$ after $\ell_{s_2} = 1$ step is $(1 - 2\tau)$, and thus $\text{Cond}_{\{s_2\}}^1(\hat{A}) = \overline{\text{Cond}}_{\{s_2\}}^1(\hat{A}) = 1 - (1 - 2\tau) = 2\tau$. Taking $A_\eta = \hat{A}$, Theorem 5 tells us that $|\mathbb{P}^A(\mathbf{F} s_2) - \mathbb{P}^{\hat{A}}(\mathbf{F} s_2)| \leq \frac{\eta}{2\tau}$. Notice that on that example, even using $\ell_{s_2} = m = 3$, we obtain $\text{Cond}_{\{s_2\}}^3(\hat{A}) = 1 - (1 - 2\tau)^3 \approx 6\tau$, and we find a similar bound $\approx \frac{3\eta}{6\tau} = \frac{\eta}{2\tau}$.

Figure 3: Three DTMCs A, \hat{A}, \hat{B} (from left to right), with $0 < \eta < 2\tau < 1$

Compare our bound with the exact difference $|\mathbb{P}^A(\mathbf{F} s_2) - \mathbb{P}^{\hat{A}}(\mathbf{F} s_2)| = \frac{2\tau + \eta}{4\tau} - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{\eta}{4\tau}$. Our upper bound only has an overhead factor of 2, even while the conditioning is particularly bad (small) in this example.

Without knowing that there are transitions from s_1 to s_2 and from s_1 to s_3 , the chance to only witness the transition from s_1 to s_1 (and consequently to learn DTMC \hat{B}) is high if the inverse of τ is large enough compared to the number of observations. For \hat{B} , we have $\text{Cond}_{S, s_2}^\ell(\hat{B}) = 1$ for all $\ell > 0$. Let $\eta = 2\tau$ and $A_\eta = \hat{B}$. Now, there is no function of η and $\text{Cond}_{S, s_2}^\ell(\hat{B})$ (without creating a moot bound of value at least $\frac{1}{2}$ for all η , $\text{Cond}(\hat{B})$) which could bound the difference $|\mathbb{P}^A(F s_2) - \mathbb{P}^{\hat{B}}(\mathbf{F} s_2)| = \frac{1}{2}$. Hence, the hypothesis on $A(i, j) \neq 0$ iff $A_\eta(i, j) \neq 0$ is necessary, which requires to know the support of the transitions of the real system A .

6.4 PAC bounds for $\sum_j |\hat{A}_W(i, j) - A(i, j)| \leq \eta$

We use Theorem 1 in order to obtain PAC bounds. We use it to estimate individual transition probabilities, rather than the probability of a property.

Let W be a set of traces drawn with respect to A such that every $\omega \in W$ is of the form $\omega = \rho \cdot s \cdot \rho' \cdot s$. For recall, for each state i, j of S , n_i^W is the number of transitions originating from i in W and n_{ij}^W is the number of transition ss' in W . Let $\delta' = \frac{\delta}{m_{\text{stoch}}}$, where m_{stoch} is the number of *stochastic* states, i.e., with at least two outgoing transitions.

We want to sample traces until the empirical transition probabilities $\frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}$ are relatively close to the exact transition probabilities a_{ij} , for all $i, j \in S$. For that, we need to determine a stopping criteria over the number of state occurrences $(n_i)_{1 \leq i \leq m}$ such that:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\exists i \in S, \sum_j \left| a_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W} \right| > \varepsilon \right) \leq \delta$$

First, note that for any observed state $i \in S$, if $a_{ij} = 0$ (or $a_{ij} = 1$), then with probability 1, $\frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W} = 0$ (respectively $\frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W} = 1$). Thus, for all $\varepsilon > 0$, $|a_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}| < \varepsilon$ with probability 1. Second, for two distinct states i and i' , the transition probabilities $\frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}$ and $\frac{n_{i'j'}^W}{n_{i'}^W}$ are independent for all j, j' .

Let $i \in S$ be a stochastic state. If we observe n_i^W transitions from i such that $n_i^W \geq \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2} \log \left(\frac{2}{\delta'} \right) \left[\frac{1}{4} - \left(\max_j \left| \frac{1}{2} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W} \right| - \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon \right)^2 \right]$, then, according to Theorem 1, $\mathbb{P} \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^m |a_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}| > \varepsilon \right) \leq \delta'$. In particular, $\mathbb{P} \left(\max_{j \in S} |a_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}| > \varepsilon \right) \leq \delta'$.

Moreover, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P} \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^m \max_{j \in S} |a_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}| > \varepsilon \right) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbb{P} \left(\max_{j \in S} |a_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W}| > \varepsilon \right) \\ &\leq m_{\text{stoch}} \delta' \\ &\leq \delta \end{aligned}$$

In other words, the probability that “there exists a state $i \in S$ such that the deviation between the exact and empirical outgoing transitions from i exceeds ε ” is bounded by δ as soon as for each state $i \in S$, n_i^W satisfies the stopping rule of the algorithm of Chen using ε and the corresponding δ' . This gives the hypothesis $\sum_j |A_\eta(i, j) - A(i, j)| \leq \epsilon$ for all state i of Section 6.2.

6.5 A Matrix \hat{A}_W accurate for all CTL properties

We now use Laplace smoothing in order to ensure the other hypothesis $A_\eta(i, j) \neq 0$ iff $A(i, j) \neq 0$ for all states i, j . For all $i \in S$, we define the Laplace offset depending on the state i as $\alpha_i = \frac{(n_i^W)^2 \varepsilon}{10 \cdot k_i^2 \max_j n_{ij}^W}$, where k_i is the number of transitions from state i . This ensures that the error from Laplace smoothing is at most one tenth of the statistical error. Let $\alpha = (\alpha_i)_{1 \leq i \leq m}$. From the sample set W , we output the matrix $\hat{A}_W^\alpha = (\hat{a}_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq m}$ with Laplace smoothing α_i for state i , i.e.:

$$\hat{a}_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}^W + \alpha_i}{n_i^W + k_i \alpha_i} \text{ if } a_{ij} \neq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{a}_{ij} = 0 \text{ otherwise}$$

It is easy to check that we have for all $i, j \in S$: $\left| \hat{a}_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W} \right| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{10 \cdot k_i}$

That is, for all state i , $\sum_j \left| \hat{a}_{ij} - \frac{n_{ij}^W}{n_i^W} \right| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{10}$. Using the triangular inequality:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\exists i \in S, \sum_j |a_{ij} - \hat{a}_{ij}| > \frac{11}{10} \varepsilon \right) \leq \delta$$

For all $i \in S$, let $H^*(n_i^W, \varepsilon, \delta') = \max_{j \in S} H(n_i^W, n_{ij}^W, \varepsilon, \delta')$ be the maximal Chen bound over all the transitions from state i . Let $B(\hat{A}_W^\alpha) = \max_{S_F} \frac{\ell_{S_F}}{\text{Cond}_{S_F}(\hat{A}_W^\alpha)}$.

Since in Theorem 5, the original model and the learned one have symmetric roles, by applying this theorem on \hat{A}_W^α , we obtain that:

Theorem 6. *Given a set W of traces, for $0 < \varepsilon < 1$ and $0 < \delta < 1$, if for all $i \in S$, $n_i^W \geq \left(\frac{11}{10} B(\hat{A}_W^\alpha) \right)^2 H^*(n_i^W, \varepsilon, \delta')$, we have for any CTL property φ :*

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(\hat{A}_W^\alpha, \varphi)| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta \tag{9}$$

Proof. First, $\hat{a}_{ij} \neq 0$ iff $a_{ij} \neq 0$, by definition of \hat{A}_W^α . Second, $\mathbb{P}(\exists i, \sum_j |a_{ij} - \hat{a}_{ij}| > \frac{11}{10}\varepsilon) \leq \delta$. We can thus apply Theorem 5 on \hat{A}_W^α, A and obtain (9) for φ any formula of the form $S_1 \mathbf{U} S_2$. It remains to show that for any formula $\varphi \in \Psi$, we can define $S_1, S_2 \subseteq S$ such that φ can be expressed as $S_1 \mathbf{U} S_2$.

Consider the different cases: If φ is of the form $\varphi = \varphi_1 \mathbf{U} \varphi_2$ (it subsumes the case $\varphi = \mathbf{F} \varphi_1 = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{U} \varphi_1$) with φ_1, φ_2 CTL formulas, we define S_1, S_2 as the sets of states satisfying φ_1 and φ_2 , and we have the equivalence (see [1] for more details). If $\varphi = X \varphi_2$, define $S_1 = \emptyset$ and S_2 as the set of states satisfying φ_2 .

The last case is $\varphi = \mathbf{G} \varphi_1$, with φ_1 a CTL formula. Again, we define S_1 the set of states satisfying φ_1 , and S_2 the set of states satisfying the CTL formula $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \varphi_1$. The probability of the set of paths satisfying $\varphi = \mathbf{G} \varphi_1$ is exactly the same as the probability of the set of paths satisfying $S_1 \mathbf{U} S_2$. \square

6.6 Algorithm

We give more details about the learning process of a Markov Chain, accurate for every CTL formula. For completeness, we also provide in the extended version, Appendix F [17] a similar algorithm for a time-to-failure property.

A path ω is observed from s_0 till a state is observed twice. Then ω is added to W and the reset operation is performed. We use Laplace smoothing to compute the corresponding matrix \hat{A}_W^α . The error bound is computed on W , and a new path ω' is then being generated if the error bound is not as small as desired.

This algorithm is guaranteed to terminate since, as traces are generated, with probability 1, n_s^W tends towards ∞ , \hat{A}_W^α tends towards A , and $B(\hat{A}_W^\alpha)$ tends towards $B(A)$.

Algorithm 1: Learning a matrix accurate for CTL

Data:
 $\mathcal{S}, s_0, \delta, \varepsilon$
1 $W := \emptyset$
2 $m = |\mathcal{S}|$
3 for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $n_s^W := 0$
4 Compute $\hat{A} := \hat{A}_W^\alpha$
5 Compute $B := B(\hat{A})$
6 **while** $\exists s \in \mathcal{S}, n_s^W < \left(\frac{11}{10}B(\hat{A})\right)^2 H^*(n_s^W, \varepsilon, \frac{\delta}{m})$ **do**
7 Generate a new trace $\omega := s_0 \rho s_1 \rho' s_1$, and reset \mathcal{S}
8 for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $n_s^W := n_s^W + n_s^{\{\omega\}}$
9 add ω to W
10 Compute $\hat{A} := \hat{A}_W^\alpha$
11 Compute $B := B(\hat{A})$
Output: \hat{A}_W^α

7 Evaluation and Discussion

In this section, we evaluate Algorithm 1 on 5 crafted systems and discuss its practical use. The objective of the evaluation is to provide some idea on how many samples would be sufficient for learning accurate DTMC estimations, and compare for different properties. We now describe the 5 systems:

Systems 1 and 2 are three-state models described in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Systems 3 (resp. 5) is a 30-state (resp. 200-states) clique in which every individual transition probability is $1/30$ (resp. $1/200$). System 4 is a 64-state system modeling failure and repair of 3 types of components (3 components each, 9 components in total), see [17], Appendix G for a full description of the system, including a Prism [20] model for the readers interested to investigate this system in details.

We tested time-to-failure properties by choosing as failure states s_3 for Systems 1, 2, 3, 5, and the state where all 9 components fail for System 4. We also tested Algorithm 1 (for full CTL logic) using the refined conditioning $\overline{\text{Cond}}$. We performed our algorithms 100 times for each model, except for full CTL on System 4, for which we only tested once since it is very time-consuming. We report our results in Table 1 for $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $\delta = 0.05$. In particular, we output for each model its number of states and transitions. For each (set of) property, we provide the average number of observations and the relative standard deviation.

The results show that we can learn more than 40000 stochastic transitions, such that the DTMC is accurate for all CTL formulas. Notice that for some particular systems such as System 4, it can take a lot of events to be observed before Algorithm 1 terminates. The reason is the presence of rare states, such as the state where all 9 components fail, which are observed with an extremely small probability. In order to evaluate the probabilities of CTL properties of the form: “if all 9 components fail, then CTL property φ is satisfied”, this state needs to be explored many times, explaining the high number of events observed before the algorithm terminates. On the other hand, for properties that do not involve the 9

	System 1	System 2	System 3	System 4	System 5
# states	3	3	30	64	200
# transitions	4	7	900	204	40000
# events for time-to-failure	191 (16%)	991 (10%)	2753 (7.4%)	1386 (17.9%)	18335 (7.2%)
# events for full CTL	1463 (12.9%)	4159 (11.7%)	8404 (3.8%)	1872863	79823 (1.7%)

Table 1: Average number of observed events N (and relative standard deviation) given $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $\delta = 0.05$ for a time-to-failure property and for the full CTL logic using the refined conditioning $\overline{\text{Cond}}$.

components failing as prior, such as time-to-failure, one does not need to observe this state even once to conclude that it has an extremely small probability to happen. This suggests that efficient algorithms could be developed for subsets of CTL formulas, e.g., in defining a subset of important events to consider. We believe that Theorem 4 and 5 could be extended to handle such cases.

Comparing results for time-to-failure (or equivalently Statistical Model Checking) and for the full CTL logic is interesting. Excluding System 4 which involves rare states, the number of events that needs to be observed varies between 4.3 to 7 times more, even for the model with 40000 transitions. Surprisingly, the highest difference is obtained on the smallest System 1. It is because every run of System 1 generated for time-to-failure is short ($s_1s_2s_1$ and $s_1s_2s_3$). However, in Systems 2,3 and 5, samples for time-to-failure can be much longer, and the performances for time-to-failure (or equivalently SMC) is not so much better than for learning a DTMC accurate for all CTL properties.

For the system we tested, the unoptimized Cond was particularly large (more than 20) because for many states s , there was probability 0 to leave $R(s)$, and hence $\ell(s)$ was quite large. These are the cases where $\overline{\text{Cond}}$ is much more efficient, as then we can choose $\ell(s) = 1$ as the probability to reach s from states in $R(s)$ is 1 ($R_1(s) = R(s)$ and $\overline{R_*(s)} = \emptyset$). We used $\overline{\text{Cond}}$ in our algorithm.

Finally, we evaluate experimental confidence by comparing the time-to-failure probabilities in the learned DTMC and the original system. We repeat our algorithms 1000 times on System 1 and 2 (with $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $\delta = 0.05$). These probabilities differ by less than ϵ respectively 999 and 995 times out of 1000. Specification (2) is thus largely fulfilled (the specification should be ensured 950 out of 1000 times), that empirically endorses our approach. Hence, while our PAC bound overapproximates the confidence in the learned system (which is unavoidable), it is not that far from experimental values.

8 Conclusion

In this paper, we provided theoretical grounds for obtaining global PAC bounds when learning a DTMC: we bound the error made between the behaviors of the model and of the system, formalized using temporal logics. While it is not possible to obtain a learning framework for LTL properties, we provide it for the whole CTL logic. For subsets of CTL, e.g. for a fixed timed-to-failure property, we obtain better bounds, as efficient as Statistical MC. Overall, this work should help in the recent trends of establishing trusted machine learning [15].

Our techniques does not require to know the minimal probability of transitions [13], which is not realistic in our context: we only need to know the set of transitions with non null probability. Our techniques also provides rationale to set the constant in Lapalace smoothing, usually left to an expert to set.

Some cases remain problematic, such as systems where states are visited very rarely. Nevertheless, we foresee potential solutions involving rare event simulation [21]. This goes beyond the scope of this work and it is left to future work.

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Appendix A Content of the Appendices

In this supplement, to ease the readability, we recall the Okamoto bound and a LTL definition in Appendix B. We provide the proof of Theorem 2 in Appendix C, the proof of Lemma 1 in Appendix D and the proof of Theorem 4 in Appendix E. For sake of completeness, we also provide the algorithm for the fixed time-to-failure property in Appendix F. Finally, we provide a more detailed description of System 4 in Appendix G.

Appendix B Some useful recalls

We recall for the readers the Okamoto inequality [22] (also called the Chernoff bound) and a definition of Linear Temporal Logic (LTL). Note however that the Okamoto inequality is not used in the paper and that our work focuses on CTL more than LTL.

Theorem 7 (Okamoto bound). *Let $\varepsilon > 0$, δ such that $0 < \delta < 1$ and $\hat{\gamma}_W$ be the crude Monte-Carlo estimator of probability γ . If $n \geq \frac{1}{2\varepsilon^2} \log\left(\frac{2}{\delta}\right)$,*

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma - \hat{\gamma}_W| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta.$$

Definition 4 (LTL). *Let $Prop$ be the set of atomic propositions. LTL is defined by the following grammar $\varphi ::= \perp \mid \top \mid p \mid \neg\varphi \mid \varphi \wedge \varphi \mid \varphi \vee \varphi \mid \mathbf{F}\varphi \mid \mathbf{G}\varphi \mid \mathbf{X}\varphi \mid \varphi \mathbf{U}\varphi$, with $p \in Prop$ and $NeXt$, \mathbf{G} lobally, \mathbf{F} inally and \mathbf{U} ntil the standard modal temporal operators.*

We refer to [1] for more details about the semantics and the grammar of this logic.

Appendix C Negative result for LTL

Theorem 2. *Given $\varepsilon > 0$, $0 < \delta < 1$, and a finite set W of paths, there is no learning strategy such that, for all LTL formula φ ,*

$$\mathbb{P}(|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi)| > \varepsilon) \leq \delta \tag{10}$$

Proof. We prove it by defining a sequence of LTL properties that violates the specification above. As we show, it only relies on a single deviation in one transition. This is thus independent of the learning strategy.

Let $s_u \in S$ be a state that can be visited arbitrarily often from s_0 and let $s_v \in S$ be a non-unique successor of s_u . Assume that $\hat{A}_W = (\hat{a}_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq m}$ is an estimate of $A = (a_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq m}$ and note $\tau > 0$ the deviation between \hat{a}_{uv} and a_{uv} . For simplicity, we assume $\hat{a}_{uv} = a_{uv} + \tau$ but a similar proof can be done with $\hat{a}_{uv} = a_{uv} - \tau$.

Let φ_n be the property “Transition $s_u s_v$ occurs at most $(a_{uv} + \tau/2)n$ times during the n first visits of s_i ”. This property is a LTL property since it can be

written as a finite composition of \mathbf{X} , \wedge and \vee (for more details, see the similar property in Section 7.2 of [12]). Let $(X_k)_{1 \leq k \leq n}$ be n independent Bernoulli random variables from the set of transitions possible in s_u to $\{0, 1\}$ assigning 1 when $s_u s_v$ is taken after the k -th visit of s_u and 0 if another transition is taken after the k -th visit of s_u . Then, we can rewrite:

$$\mathbb{P}(\varphi_n) = \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_k \leq a_{uv} + \tau/2\right) \quad (11)$$

By the law of large numbers, $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_k$ tends to a_{uv} with respect to A when n tends to the infinity. Then,

$$\gamma(A, \varphi_n) = \mathbb{P}_A\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_k \leq a_{uv} + \tau/2\right) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1.$$

But, with respect to \hat{A}_W , $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_k$ tends to $a_{uv} + \tau$. So,

$$\gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi_n) = \mathbb{P}_{\hat{A}_W}\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_k \leq a_{uv} + \tau/2\right) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0$$

Thus, $\gamma(A, \varphi_n) - \gamma(\hat{A}_W, \varphi_n) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1$ almost surely. More precisely, given $\varepsilon > 0$, δ , $0 < \delta < 1$ and a finite run W , there exists a rank N such that specification 10 can not be fulfilled for properties φ_n , $n \geq N$.

Appendix D Proof of Lemma 1 in Proposition 1

For recall, we defined $q_W(u)$ the number of occurrences of sequence u in the traces of W . Note that u can be a state, an individual transition or even a path.

Lemma 1. *For all set of traces W , there exists a set of traces W' such that:*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall s, t, \frac{q_{W'}(s \cdot t)}{q_{W'}(s)} &= \frac{q_W(s \cdot t)}{q_W(s)} \quad \wedge \\ \forall r, s, t \in V, q_{W'}(r \cdot s \cdot t) &= \frac{q_{W'}(r \cdot s) \times q_{W'}(s \cdot t)}{q_{W'}(s)} \end{aligned}$$

We use the following definitions in the proof.

Definition 2 (Equivalence). *Two sets of traces W and W' are equivalent if for all s, t , $\frac{q_W(s \cdot t)}{q_W(s)} = \frac{q_{W'}(s \cdot t)}{q_{W'}(s)}$.*

Definition 3 (s-factor). *Given a trace r and a state s , F is an s -factor of r if F is a factor of r and F starts by s . Moreover, F is elementary if it does not contain any other s .*

A trace can then be seen as a set of factors $BF_1 \dots F_k E$ where B is the special factor beginning, F_i are some s-factors for all i and E is the special ending s-factor. We can notice that for all trace r and r' obtained by permutation of the F_i , $\{r\}$ and $\{r'\}$ are equivalent. Without loss of generality, we suppose that states s_j such that there exists a transition (s_j, s) are states s_1, \dots, s_Q . In W , we denote n_i the number of transitions (s, s_i) , m_j the number of transitions (s_j, s) and $q_{i,j} = \frac{q_W(s_j \cdot s) \times q_W(s \cdot s_i)}{q_W(s)}$. $q_{i,j}$ represents then the number of times a transition (s_j, s) should be followed by a transition (s, s_i) . By definition, we have that $\sum_i n_i = \sum_j m_j = q_W(s)$ and $\forall i, j, q_{i,j} > 0$. We denote $k = q_W(s)$. Finally, for a factor F , we denote by $q_{F,i,j}$ the number of apparitions of (s_j, s, s_i) in F .

Proof. (of Lemma 1) Let us suppose that W is made of only one trace $r = BF_1 \dots F_f E$.

We prove the lemma by induction on $s \in V$, then induction on the number of predecessors of s .

Let suppose that every factor in $\{B, F_1, \dots, F_f\}$ ends with s_1 , that $f = m_1 - 1$ and that the sequence $s_1 s$ never appears neither in B nor in F_l for all l nor in E . We also suppose that $\forall i, \forall j > 1, q_{B,i,j} + \sum_{l=1}^f q_{F_l,i,j} + q_{E,i,j} = q_{i,j}$. It means that for all $j > 1$ for all i , we have $q_{W'}(s_j \cdot s \cdot s_i) = \frac{q_{W'}(s_j \cdot s) \times q_{W'}(s \cdot s_i)}{q_{W'}(s)}$ and we just have to consider s_1 .

Let r' be $BF_1 \dots F_f E$. r' is equivalent to r . We also obtain that for all $i, q_{r,i,1} = q_{i,1}$ since there are exactly $q_{i,1}$ factors starting by s_i . Furthermore, $\forall i, \forall j > 1, q_{r,i,j} = q_{B,i,j} + \sum_{l=1}^f q_{F_l,i,j} + q_{E,i,j} = q_{i,j}$. Indeed, none was added and we did not break those already existing. Then, $\forall i, \forall j, q_{W'}(s_j \cdot s \cdot s_i) = \frac{q_{W'}(s_j \cdot s) \times q_{W'}(s \cdot s_i)}{q_{W'}(s)}$.

Now, let us consider when there are J states to deal with, $J > 1$, and the factors $\{B, F_1 \dots F_f, E\}$ such that $f = \sum_{j=1}^J m_j - 1$. Besides, for all $j \leq J$, exactly m_j factors in $\{B, F_1 \dots F_f\}$ end with s_j and for all i , exactly $\sum_{j=1}^J q_{i,j}$ factors in $\{F_1 \dots F_f, E\}$ start with ss_i . Furthermore, for all $j \leq J$, the sequence $s_j s$ never appears neither in B nor in F_l for all l and for all i , for all $j > J, q_{B,i,j} + \sum_{l=1}^f q_{F_l,i,j} + q_{E,i,j} = q_{i,j}$.

We create new factors in order to deal with s_J by merging the existing one. We apply the following algorithm:

```

Merge(Factors, J)
for i from 1 to Q do
  for l from 1 to  $q_{i,J}$  do
    Choose  $F_1$  ending by  $s_J$ , a factor  $F_2 \neq F_1$  beginning by  $s_i$ , we denote
       $F' = F_1 F_2$ 
     $Factors = Factors \setminus \{F_1, F_2\} \cup \{F'\}$ 
Output: Factors

```

Since $\sum_i q_{i,j} = m_j$, there is always one factor ending by S_J that can be chosen. Let us suppose that there is no candidate for F_2 . It means that no factor other than F_1 starts by ss_i , and then $\sum_{j=1}^J q_{i,j} \leq q_{i,J}$ (number available at start smaller than number used). We deduce that for all $j < J$, $q_{i,j} = 0$ and that is absurd.

We obtain the set of factors $\{B', F'_1, \dots, F'_{f'}, E'\}$. We have merged m_J factors, then $f' = f - m_J = \sum_{j=1}^{j-1} m_j - 1$. For all $j < J$, the number of factors ending with s_j has not changed. For all i , there are $\sum_{j=1}^J q_{i,j} - q_{i,J} = \sum_{j=1}^{j-1} q_{i,j}$ factors in $\{F'_1 \dots F'_{f'}, E'\}$ starting with ss_i . Furthermore, for all $j < J$, the sequence $s_j s$ still never appears neither in B nor in F_l for all l and for all i , for all $j \geq J$, $q_{B,i,j} + \sum_{l=1}^f q_{F_l,i,j} + q_{E,i,j} = q_{i,j}$.

At start, when considering all elementary factors $\{B, F_1, \dots, F_f, E\}$, we have $f = k - 1 = \sum_{j=1}^Q m_j - 1$ and for all j , exactly m_j factors in $\{B, F_1 \dots F_f\}$ ends with s_j and for all i , exactly $\sum_{j=1}^Q q_{i,j} = n_i$ factors in $\{F_1 \dots F_f, E\}$ start with ss_i . Besides, since all factors are elementary, no sequence $s_j s$ appears in any of them and trivially, for all $j > Q$, $q_{B,i,j} + \sum_{l=1}^f q_{F_l,i,j} + q_{E,i,j} = 0$. Thus, the requirements are met.

Appendix E Proof of Theorem 4

Theorem 4. Denoting φ the property of reaching state s in DTMC A , we have:

$$|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(A_\eta, \varphi)| < \frac{\ell_s \cdot \eta}{\text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A)}$$

Proof. Let v_s be the stochastic vector with $v_s(s) = 1$. We denote $v_0 = v_{s_0}$. Let $s \in S$. We assume that $s_0 \in R_*(s)$ (else $\gamma(A, \varphi) = \gamma(A_\eta, \varphi)$ and the result is trivial). Without loss of generality, we can also assume that $A(s, s) = A_\eta(s, s) = 1$ (as we are interested in reaching s at any step). With this assumption:

$$|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(A_\eta, \varphi)| = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v_0 \cdot (A^t - A_\eta^t) \cdot v_s$$

We bound this error, through bounding by induction on t :

$$E(t) = \max_{i \in R_*(s)} v_i \cdot (A^t - A_\eta^t) \cdot v_s$$

We then have trivially:

$$|\gamma(A, \varphi) - \gamma(A_\eta, \varphi)| \leq \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} E(t)$$

Note that for $i = s$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v_i \cdot (A^t) \cdot v_s = 1 = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v_i \cdot A_\eta^t \cdot v_s$, and thus their difference is null.

Let $t \in \mathbb{N}$. We let $j \in R_*(s)$ such that $E(t) = v_j \cdot (A^t - A_\eta^t) \cdot v_s$.

By the triangular inequality, introducing the term $v_j \cdot A^{\ell_s} A_\eta^{t-k} \cdot v_s - v_j \cdot A^{\ell_s} A_\eta^{t-k} \cdot v_s = 0$, we have:

$$E(t) \leq |v_j \cdot (A_\eta^t - A^{\ell_s} A_\eta^{t-\ell_s}) \cdot v_s| + |(v_j \cdot A^{\ell_s}) \cdot (A_\eta^{t-\ell_s} - A^{t-\ell_s}) \cdot v_s|$$

We separate vector $(v_j \cdot A^m) = w_1 + w_2 + w_3$ in three sub-stochastic vectors w_1, w_2, w_3 : vector w_1 is over $\{s\}$, and thus we have $w_1 \cdot A_\eta^{t-\ell_s} = w_1 = w_1 \cdot A^{t-\ell_s}$, and the term cancels out. Vector w_2 is over states of $R_*(s)$, with $\sum_{i \in R_*(s)} w_2[i] \leq (1 - \text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A))$, and we obtain an inductive term $\leq (1 - \text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A))E(t - \ell_s)$. Last, vector w_3 is over states not in $R(s)$, and we have $w_3 \cdot A_\eta^{t-\ell_s} \cdot v_s = 0 = w_3 \cdot A^{t-\ell_s} \cdot v_s$, and the term cancels out.

We also obtain that $|v_j \cdot (A_\eta^t - A^{\ell_s} A_\eta^{t-\ell_s}) \cdot v_s| \leq \ell_s \cdot \eta$. Thus, we have the inductive formula $E(t) \leq (1 - \text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A))E(t - \ell_s) + \ell_s \cdot \eta$. It yields for all $t \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$E(t) \leq (\ell_s \cdot \eta) \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - \text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A))^i$$

$$E(t) \leq \frac{\ell_s \cdot \eta}{\text{Cond}_s^{\ell_s}(A)}$$

□

Appendix F Algorithm for the fixed time-to-failure property

A run W is observed from s_0 and every time s_0 or s_F are observed, the reset operation is performed, and a new path ω is being generated. W is the set of all those paths. In the work, we assume that the probability of reaching s_0 or s_F is 1 in order to guarantee the termination of the algorithm. since s_F is immediately followed by s_0 .

Algorithm 2: Learning a matrix accurate for time-to-failure property

```

Learning( $A, s_0, s_F, \delta, \varepsilon$ )
 $n_{\text{succ}} = 0$ 
 $n = 1$  (number of times  $s_0$  has been visited)
 $s = s_0$  (current state)
while  $n < H(n, n_{\text{succ}}, \varepsilon, \delta)$  do
     $\omega_n = s_0$  and  $W = \omega_1 \cdots \omega_n$ 
    while  $s \neq s_0$  or  $s \neq s_F$  do
        Observe the next state  $s'$  (sampled with respect to  $A$ )
        Update  $\omega_n$  and  $\hat{A}_W$ 
        if  $s' = s_0$  or  $s' = s_F$  then
            Output  $z(\omega_n, \varphi)$ ,  $n_{\text{succ}} \leftarrow n_{\text{succ}} + z(\omega_n, \varphi)$  and  $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 

```

Output: \hat{A}_W

Appendix G System 4

System 4 can be modeled with probabilistic model checker Prism² as a continuous time Markov chain (CTMC) that comprises three types (1, 2, 3) of three components each that may fail independently. Note however that we do not simulate the times between two changes of states but only the transitions between states, that lead to learn the induced DTMC instead. The components fail with rate $\lambda = 0.2$ and are repaired with rate $\mu = 1$. In addition, components are repaired with priority according to their type (type i has highest priority than type j if $i < j$). Components of type 1 and 2 are repaired simultaneously if at least two of their own type have failed. Type 3 components are repaired one by one as soon as one has failed. The probability transitions from state i to state j is given by the rate of the transition from the CTMC between state i and state j divided by the sum of all the rates of the enabled transitions from state i . The initial state is the state in which all the components are operational and the failure state is the state in which all the components are broken. We provide below the Prism code of the model for the readers who are interested to investigate this model in details:

² <http://www.prismmodelchecker.org/>

```

ctmc

const int n=3;
const double lambda = 0.2;
const double mu = 1.0;

module type1
state1 : [0..n] init 0;
[] state1 < n -> (n-state1)*lambda : (state1'=state1+1);
[] state1 >=2 -> mu : (state1'=0);
endmodule

module type2
state2 : [0..n] init 0;
[] state2 < n -> (n-state2)*lambda : (state2'=state2+1);
[] state2 >=2 & state1 < 2 -> mu : (state2'=0);
endmodule

module type3
state3 : [0..n] init 0;
[] state3 < n -> (n-state3)*lambda : (state3'=state3+1);
[] state3 > 0 & state2 < 2 & state1 < 2 -> mu : (state3'=state3-1);
endmodule

label "failure" = state1 = n & state2 = n & state3 = n;

```